

NUTRI•KNOW

STRUVITE (IT)

GAS LOOP (IT)

RENURE (BE)

SOS_AQUAE
(IT)

POCKETBOER 2
(BE)

FERTICOOP-GO
(ES)

Grass2Algae
(BE)

Manure
Management
Tool (ES)

MOPS (IE)

Slurry
Concentrator
(ES)

Duncannon Blue
Flag Farming (IE)

Biorefinery
Glas (IE)

Exchanging easy-to-understand nutrient management knowledge with farmers

NUTRI-KNOW aims to improve nutrient management practices in agriculture by establishing an ongoing cycle of knowledge exchange for the benefit of both farmers and the environment.

Costs assessment of ammonia air treatment in pig livestock for nitrogen recovery

Gas Loop has developed and monitored an air washing system that removes ammonia from the air of animal housing and recovers it in an ammonium sulphate solution. This increases animal welfare and productivity due to better air quality inside the pig housing.

Economic assessment

The economic viability of this innovation has been assessed in terms of the impact on value of kg meat produced by applying the ammonia air treatment system (Figure 1). Furthermore, in a case study costs have been assessed in case of construction of a pig barn equipped with the ammonia air treatment system and in case of building arrangement to accommodate the air treatment system afterwards.

Costs rate of kg meat produced

The treatment system involves cost of 0.15 - 0.17 €/kg of live weight sold, i.e., an impact of 7.3% on the sales value (related to the quotation of 2.27 €/kg CUN pigs, December 2023).

Costs of air treatment system installation

- Total installation (treatment plus building arrangement): 208,000 € - 16.2% of total pig barn costs
- Only building arrangement for installation afterwards: 28,000 € - 13.5% of total installation cost

Main benefits

The ammonia air treatment system allows the production of an ammonium sulphate solution as a liquid inorganic fertilizer, which avoids the emission of greenhouse gases due to the industrial synthesis of nitrogen. Moreover, it reduces ammonia emissions by 54%.

Figure 1. Cost items and their percentage impact on the annual management costs (productive costs increment equal to 0.16 cents per kg meat)

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